

From countries to cities: assessing climate ambition with a multi-level fair-share allocation framework

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Abstract

Local governments are widely adopting voluntary emissions targets to do their fair share of global mitigation efforts to limit global warming to 1.5°C. However, while the fair share literature is commonly used to assess and set the ambition of national emissions pledges, it remains unclear for cities and subnational governments. This article presents the first multi-level framework that derives fair share emissions allocations consistent across national and subnational governments globally. We derive emissions pathways for all countries and 3,552 local governments worldwide, based on the Paris Agreement's equity principles, and compare them to the current emissions targets from 160 subnational governments and 68 cities to assess their ambition. We find that local-level targets are often more ambitious than their national counterparts, yet achieving their fair shares will require considerably more ambitious commitments accompanied by financial support. Our results can be used to benchmark climate targets against globally consistent fair-share trajectories and strengthen vertical and horizontal cooperation through regulatory and financial support internationally and across government levels.

28 Introduction

29 National, subnational and city governments are adopting emissions targets to do their fair share of
30 the global effort needed to achieve the Paris Agreement goals. Yet there is widespread inconsistency
31 in how these fair shares are determined and how ambitious these targets are in relation to global
32 objectives.

33 Under the Paris Agreement, countries are required to provide emissions targets of the highest possible
34 ambition, reflecting equity and their Common but Differentiated Responsibilities and Respective
35 Capabilities (CBDR-RC), and explain how these are fair and ambitious. Equity and CBDR-RC are
36 enshrined in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) based on
37 articles of the Rio Convention and reaffirmed in the Paris Agreement, and as such, have become
38 principles of international environmental law^{1,2}. Countries' pledged emission reduction targets in their
39 Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) fall far short of their fair share of the remaining emissions
40 space consistent with the Paris Agreement²⁻⁵. Extensive research has advanced methods for
41 quantifying national fair shares by allocating the remaining emissions space among countries based
42 on equitable effort-sharing principles⁶⁻¹¹, most commonly based on the historical responsibility and
43 financial capability of their populations^{2,3,6,9}. Such fair shares provide a framing increasingly used by
44 civil society¹², diplomats^{13,14} and courts^{5,15,16} to evaluate whether national emissions targets are
45 consistent with the collective requirements of the Paris Agreement. As noted by legal scholars and
46 summarized by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), "it is only in relation to such a
47 'fair share' that the adequacy of a state's contribution can be assessed in the context of a global
48 collective action problem"^{2,17}.

49 Beyond national actors, cities and local governments have adopted voluntary emissions pledges at
50 scale¹⁸ – over 3,000 cities and 173 regional governments – and these commitments contribute
51 materially to the Paris goals¹⁸⁻²⁰, particularly in contexts where higher levels of government take
52 insufficient action. Here, we name 'subnational', or 'local', all governments below the national level,
53 and 'regional', governments just below the national level, which includes states, regions, and
54 provinces. The role of local governments and their emissions targets is prominent in contexts when
55 higher levels of government take insufficient action. For instance, in 2017 the "We are still in" coalition
56 of U.S. states, cities, and other non-state actors emerged in reaction to the U.S. withdrawal from the
57 Paris Agreement²¹. An analysis showed that their emissions targets, fully implemented, accounted for
58 potentially half of the U.S.'s original NDC². Transnational alliances of local governments, with growing
59 influence on UN climate negotiations, increasingly promote fair share methods for their members to
60 claim Paris-aligned ambition²²⁻²⁴.

61 However, it remains unclear what constitutes a fair share of emissions for cities and other subnational
62 governments. The limited literature mostly originates from alliances of subnational governments, such
63 as C40 Cities, which provide fair-shares allocations only for few governments worldwide and overlooks
64 how fair shares can be implemented more broadly and in diverse contexts. In practice, many local
65 governments have set emissions objectives using various fair share allocation methods^{25,26}
66 (Supplementary Information), some of which are endorsed by the influential Science Based Targets
67 Network (SBTN), despite documented methodological shortcomings that risk rewarding inaction^{2,6}.
68 Yet these approaches often apply national equity frameworks to non-sovereign local actors without
69 considering the governance implications. Local governments do not exercise full control over emission
70 sources or fiscal resources, and achieving their fair shares often depends on vertical coordination with
71 other levels of government. As a result, subnational targets may either be insufficient or infeasible,
72 making their ambition difficult to interpret. The absence of jointly derived national and subnational
73 allocations further limits systematic comparisons of local ambition relative to national targets.

74 A multilevel allocation framework is therefore needed to assess local fair shares and clarify the vertical
75 and horizontal governance arrangements required to achieve them; however, no such framework
76 currently exists. Because subnational governments vary in their autonomy, their ability to contribute
77 to fair mitigation efforts is thus inherently limited. Importantly, allocating mitigation burdens
78 according to responsibility and capability implies financial transfers to support mitigation elsewhere—
79 something that local governments often cannot easily independently mobilize. Achieving fair share
80 allocations therefore requires engaging several levels of government and international cooperation.
81 Existing analyses are limited to a few large cities and do not derive national and local emissions
82 allocations jointly, making it difficult to compare local governments’ ambition to that of their national
83 counterparts.

84 To address this gap, we develop a multilevel emissions allocation framework and derive equity-based,
85 or fair share, emissions allocations for 208 countries and territories, 3,318 regions, and 278 cities. We
86 provide emissions allocations that account for the historical responsibility and financial capability of
87 their populations and countries’ CBDR-RC^{1,2,6}. We find that most national and available regional level
88 emissions targets remain greatly insufficient to constitute a fair share of the Paris goals, with
89 exceptions of national targets in Latin America, sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. Regional and city
90 level targets tend to be more ambitious than national ones, in Brazil, Europe, India and China. The
91 stringency of fair shares implies important international financial support at the national and
92 subnational levels. Finally, we discuss how vertical and horizontal cooperation can contribute to
93 achieving these fair shares, and the global climate goals.

94 By deriving subnational allocations nested in national ones, we enable systematic comparison of
95 target ambition within and across countries and provide a coherent benchmark for assessing “Paris
96 alignment.” Our results can support cities and local governments worldwide that already commit to
97 do their fair share of global climate goals despite the absence of a methodology to set and achieve
98 their emissions targets.

99 **Modelling a multi-level equity-based allocation framework**

100 Allocations of the remaining emissions space are commonly used as a proxy for distributing the
101 mitigation effort across countries^{6,7,10,11,27,28}. For decades, principles of equity have been modelled to
102 inform international negotiations on national emissions targets and discussed in the philosophical
103 literature^{1,9,29,30}. Some modelling approaches reflect national preferences^{6,31,32}, while others are
104 developed in collaboration with civil society organizations^{7,12}. The quantitative fair share literature is
105 typically based on three equity dimensions^{1,3,10,27,33}: capability (richer countries should provide more
106 effort), responsibility (countries with high historical emissions do more), and equality (often modelled
107 as equal per capita allocation of the remaining efforts – although this has been criticized as ‘equality
108 for unequals’^{1,2}). Others have held that additional justice considerations that reflect transitional
109 justice, prioritarianism, and right to development are under-represented¹. In terms of legal
110 obligations, the Paris Agreement explicitly requires its implementation to reflect equity and the
111 principle of CBDR-RC. By contrast, equality, modelled as an equal per capita allocation of the remaining
112 emissions space or equal mitigation efforts, does not reflect countries’ CBDR-RC². For the purposes of
113 this paper, we focus on modelling equity based on the principles of responsibility and capabilities
114 countries’ obligations under the Paris Agreement and international environmental law^{2,5,6}.

115 Some studies suggest that a moderate grandfathering approach, which allocates future emissions
116 rights proportionally to current emissions, may be justified on realist grounds because it may be more
117 accepted by high emitters³⁴. While some present the grandfathering approach as pragmatic for local

118 governments, its implementability remains unexamined^{22,35}. Moreover, grandfathering is
119 incompatible with international law² and ethical considerations¹ as it penalizes the poorest countries.
120 A growing body of work shows that all continuous allocation methods starting from present emissions
121 levels embed a grandfathering bias.² Avoiding this bias requires discontinuous emissions allocation
122 approaches⁶ together with immediate international finance. In practice, countries with stringent,
123 sometimes negative, allocations should implement domestic measures of the highest possible
124 ambition³⁶, as required by the Paris Agreement, and support additional mitigation overseas that
125 counts towards their fair share^{6,17,37}. Recipient countries can then fund emission reduction beyond
126 their fair share of mitigation efforts.

127 Collectively, countries can then reduce domestic emissions in line with a given global socioeconomic
128 scenario based on feasibility considerations – and possibly cost-optimal – while effectively funding
129 emissions reductions in line with equity-based emissions allocations^{6,38,39}. Equitable international
130 support can then be calculated as “the difference between equity-based national emissions scenarios
131 and national domestic emissions scenarios”¹⁷. In principle, such International Trading of Mitigation
132 Outcomes (ITMOs) can be implemented under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement, which sets rules for
133 the use of market-based approaches or bilateral agreements. The use of trading mechanisms requires
134 corresponding adjustments to avoid double counting and scrutiny to ensure the integrity of the
135 mitigation outcomes.

136 At the local level, emissions targets often remain strictly domestic in scope, as local governments
137 generally have limited ability to finance emissions reductions overseas. Consequently, methodologies
138 used to derive local emissions allocations and targets either simply acknowledge that such allocations
139 cannot be met²⁴ or downplay equity considerations through grandfathering while still describing the
140 resulting targets as “Paris-Aligned”⁴⁰. For example, the Deadline-2020 report,²⁴ commissioned by the
141 C40 Cities for Climate Leadership Network, models city-level trajectories that begin at current levels
142 and converge to net-zero in 2050. The report acknowledges that these trajectories result in a collective
143 overshoot of their fair budget by 140%. Likewise, World Wildlife Fund’s One Planet City Challenge
144 models differentiated mitigation rates from current levels based on cities’ Human Development Index,
145 without accounting for their historical emissions²³. A study developed with cities of the United
146 Kingdom likewise applied a grandfathering approach²² without accounting for their capability or
147 responsibility. SBTN recommends all three methods for aligning with the Paris Agreement’s 1.5°C goal.
148 Nearly 450 of these cities have explicitly reported using these so-called ‘science-based targets’ (Fig.
149 S1). A recent study combined some fairness considerations with feasibility considerations within the
150 European Union’s regulatory context⁴¹.

151 In this study, we allocate dynamically the emissions of global cost-optimal reduction scenarios,
152 excluding emissions from land use (LULUCF) and international bunkers. We use the IPCC’s Illustrative
153 Mitigation Pathways Low Demand (IMP-LD) as a scenario limiting warming to 1.5°C (likelihood >50%)
154 with no or limited overshoot and the Gradual Strengthening (IMP-GS) as a 2°C scenario (>67%
155 likelihood to peak warming below 2°C)⁴² (Methods). The allocation approaches developed here can be
156 applied to any global emissions scenario. However, the choice of the global scenario, and its social and
157 technological assumptions, entails fairness implications outside the scope of this study⁴³. Alternative
158 approaches based on carbon budgets are well suited to track emissions overshoot but do not reflect
159 forward-looking global feasibility considerations and require additional normative assumptions on the
160 actor’s use of their budgets over time^{6,28}.

161 To reflect the CBDR-RC of the entities considered, we use allocations methods based on the historical
162 responsibility and the financial capability of their populations. At the national level, we model fair
163 share allocations as the average of two methods, responsibility and capability. Statistical combinations

164 of this kind are common in the literature^{7,8,14} but they require normative decisions about how much
165 weight to assign each principle, which can be avoided using principled combinations^{3,6,44}. Under the
166 responsibility approach, emissions are allocated on the basis of equal cumulative per capita emissions,
167 where each country receives a share of the global emissions space proportional to its population, for
168 the 1970-2100 period (see Methods and Fig. S4 for responsibility since 1990). Separately, we model a
169 capability approach adapted from a commonly applied formula^{6,8,9,45}, where emissions allocations are
170 inversely proportional to GDP per capita.

171 Subnational allocations are then derived iteratively from the national level using only the capability
172 allocation method for two reasons. Firstly, wealth-based effort-sharing is commonly embedded in
173 taxation systems. Secondly, a responsibility approach is ill-suited for cities and small highly urbanized
174 regions that have very low territorial per capita emissions, partly at the expense of rural areas⁴¹. A
175 responsibility approach may nevertheless still be meaningful for large autonomous states such as US
176 states. In practice, a local government's financial capability is influenced by the degree of
177 centralization, not accounted for here, as high national taxation can redistribute wealth among local
178 actors.

180
 181 **Figure 1 | Subnational emissions allocations across government levels.** (a) Allocation time series and variability across scales
 182 for city- (green), state- or regional- (blue), and national-level (red) in China, the EU (black), India, Kenya, and the USA. The
 183 fair share allocation based on responsibility since 1970 and capability at the national level, with 2030 allocations shown in
 184 (b), and then downscaled subnationally based on capability, with 2030 levels shown in (c).

185

186 **Comparison across geographies**

187 Capability allocations initially favor poorer countries, granting them larger shares of the global
 188 emissions space, but converge toward very low levels for all actors by the end of the century (Fig. 1a).
 189 By contrast, the responsibility approach allocates negative emissions rights to high historical emitters
 190 but large positive allocations for regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. The resulting
 191 averaged national allocations are negative for most countries in 2030, except in Sub-Saharan Africa
 192 and South Asia (Fig. 1b). While allocations vary greatly across countries, often by several times
 193 present-day emissions levels, differences within countries remain relatively smaller, except in South
 194 America, Africa and South Asia (Fig. 1c). For local actors, whose allocations broadly reflect national

195 contexts, these findings suggest that achieving fair targets requires multi-level cooperation and
 196 financial redistribution across jurisdictions.

197

198 **Ambition assessment of emissions targets**

199

200 **Figure 2 | Fair share emissions allocations compared to historical emissions and emissions targets at the national, regional**
 201 **and city-level for Kolkata, Paris and San Francisco** (all available results in SI). The emissions targets of India, West Bengal
 202 and Kolkata are aligned with their 1.5°C allocations. The targets of France in 2050, Ile de France in 2050 and Paris in 2030 are
 203 in line with their 2°C allocations, but their short-term emissions remain too high. The targets of the USA (before withdrawing
 204 from the Paris Agreement), California and San Francisco are greatly insufficient to meet negative allocations.

205

206

207 **Figure 3 | Geography of ambition assessment of the 2030 emissions targets of national (a) and local governments (b).**

208 National allocations are the average of an allocation based on historical responsibility since 1970 and financial capability,

209 applied to two scenarios limiting warming to 1.5°C and 2°C. Allocations from the national to subnational levels are based on

210 their financial capability only.

211 Importantly, our framework also enables cities and subnational governments to consistently assess

212 and compare the ambition of their targets in relation to 1.5°C and 2°C scenarios. For example, the

213 targets of Kolkata, West Bengal and India are aligned with their fair share of the 1.5°C pathway (Fig.

214 2, additional results in SI). The targets of France in 2050, Ile de France in 2050 and Paris in 2030 are in

215 line with their 2°C allocations, but their short-term emissions remain too high. The targets of the USA

216 (before withdrawing from the Paris Agreement), California and San Francisco are greatly insufficient

217 to meet negative allocations. At the national level, only countries with the lowest GDP per capita and

218 historical emissions have targets within their 1.5°C-allocations (Fig. 3a). At the local level, we find that

219 188 entities have set 2030 emission targets that are no more ambitious than those of their national

220 governments, suggesting alignment with the same underlying global pathway (Fig. 3b,). In contrast,

221 only 26 entities located in countries like Brazil, Europe, Japan, and China have adopted more ambitious

222 targets. Only 2 of the subnational entities analyzed has set a target less ambitious than its national

223 counterpart both located in India. This comparison is based on assumptions regarding their boundary

224 definitions, emissions targets, reference year, scope and conditionality on vertical or horizontal

225 cooperation¹⁸ (Methods).

226 Discussion

227 Although the Paris Agreement recognizes the importance of climate action across all levels of
228 government, it remains unclear how equitable climate responsibility should be distributed among
229 them⁴⁶. Here, we derive emissions allocations that are mutually consistent across government levels
230 and grounded in equity. Unlike existing methods widely used by alliances of cities and local
231 actors^{22,24,40,47}, our discontinuous allocation approach avoids the grandfathering effects that can dilute
232 equity from the outset. These allocations provide a basis for governments to set targets consistent
233 with the Paris Agreement's temperature goals, and for observers to benchmark existing targets
234 against 1.5°C or 2°C pathways. At the same time, because fair-share allocations are derived
235 independently of territorial, technical, and political feasibility, local governments may be unable to
236 deliver them through domestic action alone without supportive cooperation mechanisms⁴⁸. This
237 challenge raises a central question for multilevel climate governance: how can local governments
238 contribute to achieving the Paris Agreement when their fair-share allocations are, in some cases,
239 immediately negative.

240 The necessity of vertical and horizontal cooperation

241 Central to achieving fair share allocations is the extent to which local governments can regulate the
242 emissions sources within their territories and the degree to which they depend on vertical
243 cooperation. Already, one quarter of cities report that their emissions target is conditional on policies
244 beyond their control⁴⁹. A separate analysis of similar scope found that fewer than 40% of cities
245 pledging largely voluntary emission targets are on track to meet their objectives⁵⁰. A major reason for
246 the lack of implementation progress is the lack of financing. For example, the city of Valencia, Spain,
247 which joined the EU Cities Mission programme⁵¹ targeting net-zero emissions in 2030 well ahead of
248 national commitments, estimated that it could only fund 7% of its implementation plan⁵². While the
249 importance of vertical cooperation to implement ambitious local policies (labelled 'Highest domestic
250 ambition' in Fig. 3) is well established, staying within a local fair share allocation requires additional
251 international horizontal cooperation (striped in Fig. 3), a dimension that has so far been largely
252 overlooked in the literature on local fair shares.

253 To achieve their fair share, national and local governments will need to provide or access international
254 support, which will require enabling policies and support from other government levels (Fig. 3).
255 Through horizontal cooperation, governments with large allocations could receive support to reduce
256 their domestic emissions beyond their fair share allocations. While financial constraints are frequently
257 raised by local governments^{24,52}, some cities already use national offsets to achieve early net-zero
258 objectives, as early as 2020 for Melbourne^{53,54}, showing openness to fund extraterritorial mitigation.

259 Financial capacity and international support

260 The financial capacity and political agency of local governments depend on the degree of
261 centralization within their governance structure. Although international support typically falls within
262 the purview of national governments, local entities can still complement these efforts and advocate
263 for national governments to close the emissions gap needed to achieve their local fair share (Fig. 3).
264 Conversely, recipient governments can clarify the regulatory and financial support they require to
265 fulfill their emissions allocation.

266 Through national or international alliances such as C40, ICLEI, EU Mission Cities, local governments
267 encourage the adoption of Paris-aligned targets and the cooperation they require, while mobilizing
268 other government levels to provide regulatory and financial support. Announced at COP28, the UN's
269 Coalition for High Ambition Multilevel Partnerships (CHAMP) initiative aims at strengthening

270 cooperation between national and local actors and improving access to climate finance at the local
 271 level. The discretionary use of traded mitigation outcomes to achieve an emissions objective, possibly
 272 under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement at the national level, is distinct from the other financial
 273 obligations³⁸, including under Article 9⁵⁵. Importantly, the purchase of mitigation outcomes should
 274 complement, rather than hinder, the implementation of domestic targets of the highest possible
 275 ambition³⁶. Additionally, having emissions targets with similar ambition across governments can
 276 contribute to harmonizing initial conditions when linking corporate emissions markets (local markets
 277 or Mitigation Contribution Units not authorized for transfer under national accounting), which reduces
 278 leakage and increases efficiency⁵⁶.

279 **Limitations**

280 The broad coverage of this study implies limitations. Most importantly, the present fair-share
 281 calculations do not reflect the varying degree of local government agency worldwide or their level of
 282 centralization. Assessing the ambition of emissions targets may be less meaningful for small
 283 governments in centralized countries, since they have limited capacity to implement or fund emissions
 284 reductions. A practical improvement would be to distribute a country's mitigation effort across its
 285 different levels of government in proportion to their share of public budgets instead of their GDP. The
 286 focus on territorial emissions implies additional efforts are needed to address extraterritorial
 287 emissions, such as through consumption-based emissions⁴¹ and Scope 2 emissions.

288

289

290 **Figure 3 | Conceptual framework for the implementation of fair shares at the national level (a) and across government**
 291 **levels (b).** a. At the national level, countries can meet their fair share through a combination of domestic mitigation (filled)
 292 and international trading of mitigation outcomes (striped) to equitably fund mitigation where it is the cheapest. b. Across
 293 government levels, allocations can be met through emissions reductions by the jurisdiction itself in cooperation with other
 294 levels of government (filled) and through cooperation with other governments overseas, providing or receiving funding
 295 (striped). Achieving equity-based allocations requires vertical cooperation through regulation and funding and horizontal
 296 cooperation with financial support across local governments. Vertical cooperation is also needed to manage the provision or
 297 use of international finance. When local governments lack resources to provide sufficient finance to meet their fair shares,
 298 they could advocate for its provision on their behalf by higher government levels.

299 **Conclusion**

300 National and local governments have adopted emissions targets, often presented as fair contributions
301 to the Paris Agreement's emissions goal and its equity requirement to account for countries'
302 responsibility and capability. The fair share literature mostly focuses on national-level allocations and
303 only derives local allocations disconnected from other levels of government. This study presents the
304 first multilevel emissions allocation framework, grounded in the Paris Agreement's goal and equity
305 principle. It provides the most comprehensive set of allocations for nearly all 3,318 state-level actors
306 and 234 cities. When compared to existing emissions targets, these allocations provide the first
307 ambition assessment framework consistent across levels of government for states and cities
308 worldwide. These allocations can inform governments that seek to pledge fair and ambitious
309 contributions to the Paris Agreement goals, possibly despite the lack of their country's efforts. Ex post,
310 our results serve as fairness and ambition benchmarks of national and local emissions targets. To meet
311 these fair share allocations, horizontal cooperation is needed through contributions from national and
312 local governments with higher capacity and historical responsibility to fund mitigation in other
313 jurisdictions. Vertical cooperation is most needed for the lowest government levels, particularly in
314 highly centralized governments, to implement and fund mitigation in line with their allocation. Large
315 local governments with large autonomy, such as US states, may be able to fund the realization of their
316 fair share alone, while others require important support from higher government levels. This work
317 highlights the role of local governments in advancing climate action beyond their domestic emissions.
318 By coordinating with higher levels of government and engaging with horizontal mitigation support
319 (i.e., networks), local actors can contribute to an equitable climate transition beyond their territory.

320

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325

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331 **Data Availability and Code Availability statements:** Results will be available on the interactive
332 website: <https://paris-equity-check.org>. On publication results will be deposited to Data-Driven
333 EnviroLab public repository at <https://dataverse.unc.edu/dataverse/datadrivenlab>. Emission source
334 data is available at https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset_ghg80. The population data is available at
335 <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/data/projects/gpw>. Administrative boundaries are available at
336 <https://gadm.org/>. Analysis was performed using custom scripts in R (4.3.1) for allocation calculation
337 and visualization. Source code is available for review at the following link:
338 https://github.com/datadrivenenvirolab/Subnational_Equity_Allocations_Paper/releases/tag/submission
339 [ssion](#)

340 **Methods and data**

341 **Allocation methods**

342 In this study, we derive simple allocation methods that reflect CBDR-RC by accounting for the
343 responsibilities and capabilities of the populations of the entities considered. Within countries, these
344 concepts of equity are often embedded in wealth-based taxation for capability, while responsibility
345 underpins the polluter-pays principle. Conceptually, each principle can be applied consistently across
346 different levels of government, or, alternatively, different principles may be applied at the national
347 and subnational levels^{22,57}. Here, national allocations are calculated as the average of their
348 responsibility and capability allocations. Subnational allocations are then derived from the national
349 level using the capability allocation method.

350 **Responsibility approach**

351 To ensure equal cumulative per capita allocation across jurisdictions, this approach uses historical and
352 projected data of population and emissions since a selected date. . We account for historical emissions
353 only since 1970. Other studies consider emissions since 1950 or even 1850, and our results are thus
354 less stringent for countries with high historical emissions. In the Supplementary Information, we
355 provide results accounting for responsibility since 1990 as a conservative basis for assessing non-
356 compliance with the Paris Agreement (Fig. S4).

357 Firstly, for the total considered period since a selected date and until 2100, the total budget of each
358 country is calculated as a share of the global emissions budget proportionally to its total cumulative
359 population. Then, each country's budget is discounted of its past emissions since the selected date to
360 calculate its remaining budget B_{gvt} and the remaining global budget B_{global} , which is equal to the
361 cumulative emissions of the selected socio-economic scenario:

$$362 \quad B_{global} = \sum_{t=t_1}^{2100} E_{global}(t) \quad (1)$$

363 and

$$364 \quad B_{gvt} = \sum_{t=t_0}^{t_n} E_{global}(t) \cdot \frac{\sum_{t_0}^{t_n} P_{gvt}(t)}{\sum_{t_0}^{t_n} P_{global}(t)} - \sum_{t_0}^{t_1} E_{gvt}(t) \quad (2)$$

365

366 where, $t_0 = 1970$, $t_1 = 2022$ and $t_n = 2100$.

367 Alternatively written as

$$368 \quad B_{gvt} = (Hist_{global} + B_{global}) \cdot \sum_{t=t_0}^{t_n} \frac{Pop_{gvt}(t)}{Pop_{global}(t)} - Hist_{gvt} \quad (3)$$

369

370 Where $E_{gvt}(t)$ and $E_{global}(t)$ represent the national and global emissions over time, Pop
371 represents their population over time and $Hist$ represents their cumulative historical emissions.
372 $E_{global}(t)$ is the global emissions trajectory that starts with historical emissions levels and is extended
373 with the mitigation scenario of choice (e.g., a 1.5°C trajectory) after 2022.

374 Then, the projected global emissions scenario (land-use emissions excluded) E_{global} is separated into
 375 its positive $E_{global>0}$ and its negative part $E_{global<0}$, emissions from Carbon Dioxide Removal and
 376 Direct Air Capture. The allocations of the global positive emissions and the global negative emissions
 377 are derived separately and then added up for each entity.

378 **Step 1.** Each country with a negative remaining budget, called $B_{gvt<0}$, is allocated a share of the
 379 negative part of the global emissions scenario $E_{global<0}$ proportional to their budget $B_{gvt<0}$.

$$380 \quad E_{gvt<0}(t) = \frac{B_{gvt<0}}{B_{global<0}} \cdot E_{global<0}(t), \forall t > t_1 \quad (4)$$

381

382 Then update these national budgets to account for this allocation:

$$383 \quad B_{gvt>0} = B_{gvt} - B_{gvt<0} \quad (5)$$

$$384 \quad B_{global>0} = B_{global} - B_{global<0} \quad (6)$$

385

386 **Step 2.** Each country is simply allocated a share of the positive global trajectories proportionally to
 387 their remaining budget $B_{gvt>0}$:

$$388 \quad E_{gvt>0}(t) = \frac{B_{gvt>0}}{B_{global>0}} \cdot E_{global>0}(t), \forall t > t_1 \quad (7)$$

389

390 For countries that were allocated negative trajectories in Step 1, add the allocation of Step 2.

$$391 \quad E_{gvt}(t) = E_{gvt<0}(t) + E_{gvt>0}(t), \forall t > t_1 \quad (8)$$

392

393 Countries with high historical emissions, and thus a negative remaining emissions budget, will have
 394 highly negative allocation in the near term. In this study, the allocation method is only applied to the
 395 country level but can be applied down any government level. In that case, the allocation of a given
 396 government does not depend on the number of government levels. It is the same when calculated
 397 directly from the global emissions pathway or iteratively across government levels.

398 Global positive, negative, and net emissions are shown in Fig. S1, and regional results in Fig. S2,3

399 **Capability approach**

400 The capability approach is based on the population and financial capability of an entity. We use GDP
 401 to represent national financial capability and Gross Regional Product (GRP) to represent subnational
 402 financial capability. The allocation is run iteratively across lower government levels and depends on
 403 the number of intermediate iterations to the chosen entity (unlike the responsibility approach). This
 404 approach may be less representative of entities' capabilities when wealth is strongly redistributed at
 405 higher levels of government. Like for the responsibility approach, this approach allocates the positive
 406 and negative emissions space separately. From the global to the national level, the positive part of the
 407 global emissions scenario is allocated proportionally to its population over the GDP per capita^{8,45}. The
 408 negative part of the global emissions scenario is allocated proportionally to the entity's GDP (equal to
 409 population times GDP per capita).

410 The national level capability allocation $E_c(t)$, where the subscript c refers to the country of interest,
 411 is:

$$412 \quad E_c(t) = E_{global>0}(t) \cdot \frac{\frac{Pop_c(t)^2}{GDP_c(t)}}{\sum_{i=countries} \frac{Pop_i(t)^2}{GDP_i(t)}} + E_{global<0}(t) \cdot \frac{GDP_c(t)}{\sum_{i=countries} GDP_i(t)} \quad (9)$$

413 The national emissions allocations $E_{country}$ presented in the manuscript are the average of the
 414 responsibility and capability national allocations. These national allocations, average of capability and
 415 responsibility allocations, are then allocated across regions using the same capability approach.
 416 Subnational level emissions $E_s(t)$, where the subscript s refers to the subnational government just
 417 below the national level:

$$418 \quad E_s(t) = E_{country>0}(t) \cdot \frac{\frac{Pop_s(t)^2}{GDP_s(t)}}{\sum_{i=states} \frac{Pop_i(t)^2}{GDP_i(t)}} + E_{country<0}(t) \cdot \frac{GDP_s(t)}{\sum_{i=states} GDP_i(t)} \quad (10)$$

419 Where $E_{country>0}$ is the positive part of the national allocation $E_{country}$, and $E_{country<0}$ its negative
 420 part. This formula is applied again down from the region to the city level for the cities. At that level,
 421 we treat the region as made only of the cities with available data, while the rest of the region is treated
 422 as a single entity that has the rest of the region's emissions, population and GDP.

$$423 \quad E_{city}(t) = E_{region>0}(t) \cdot \frac{\frac{Pop_{city}(t)^2}{GDP_{city}(t)}}{\sum_i \frac{Pop_i(t)^2}{GDP_i(t)}} + E_{region<0}(t) \cdot \frac{GDP_{city}(t)}{\sum_i GDP_i(t)} \quad (11)$$

424 Where $E_{region>0}$ is the positive part of the regional allocation E_{region} , and $E_{region<0}$ its negative part
 425 and where i includes the cities considered and the rest of the region treated as a single entity.
 426

427 **Data**

428 **GHG emissions**

429 National and subnational emissions are derived by the spatially resolved territorial emissions data
 430 from the EDGAR database, considering the spatially defined jurisdiction boundaries. Subnational
 431 jurisdiction boundaries are derived from the Global Administrative (GADM) database (v4.1 at
 432 <https://gadm.org>), including 3662 subnational jurisdictions in 240 countries and territories (ISO 3166-
 433 1 alpha-3). The number of subnational jurisdictions for each country is listed in the Supplementary
 434 Data. The geographic resolution is 0.1° by 0.1°, which is about 11 km maximum at the equator. This
 435 limitation impacts the precision of the results for geographically small territories in areas with highly
 436 variable population, emissions sources, or GDP sources. Here, we focus on territorial emissions (i.e.,
 437 Scope 1 emissions) since these are additive across government levels and up to the national level
 438 covered by the NDCs, even though Scope 2 and 3 emissions are encouraged for city-level emission
 439 inventories. EDGAR stands as one of the only consistently developed GHG emission databases, which
 440 can be used for robust subnational analysis⁵⁸.

441 The number of regions/states/provinces (3318) corresponds to the highest administrative division in
442 208 countries and territories from the GADM, while the 278 cities correspond to a non-exhaustive list
443 of cities from the Urban Environmental and Social Inclusion Index (UESI; uesi.datadrivenlab.org). The
444 278 cities are located in 247 regions/states/provinces and the latter in 93 countries, with a total
445 aggregated population of 803.73 million people.

446 We include three major greenhouse gasses in our analysis, namely carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane
447 (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O). The three GHGs together contributed 97.4% of the total GHG
448 emissions⁵⁹ in 2022. The CO₂ emissions resulting from the combustion of fossil fuels, accounting for
449 71.6% of global GHG emissions. We did not include emissions from Land Use, Land Use Change and
450 Forestry (LULUCF) in our analysis as countries' pledges use different accounting methods, and land-
451 use emissions are ill-suited for equity-based allocations given their geographic determinations^{14,60}.
452 Territorial emissions (i.e., Scope 1 emissions) are used in our analysis since this is the scope of
453 emissions that the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) submitted to the Paris Agreement by
454 countries. Global Warming Potential over a 100-year period (GWP-100) from IPCC-AR5 is used to
455 convert all GHGs to CO₂-equivalent⁵⁹. The negative emissions here refer to emissions captured through
456 Carbon Dioxide Removal (excluding those from LULUCF) and Direct Air Capture.

457 **Population**

458 Both population and GDP data at the subnational level are obtained by overlaying gridded raster data
459 with GADM administrative boundary data. Historical population data from 1970 to 2000 is from Global
460 Population Count Grid Time Series Estimates, which provide a decadal back-cast time series of
461 population grids (with spatial resolution 1/120° by 1/120°, approximately 30 m at the equator) based
462 on the year 2000 population grid from Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC)'s Global
463 Rural-Urban Mapping Project, Version 1 (GRUMPv1) dataset⁶¹. Historical population data from 2000
464 to 2020 is from Gridded Population of the World (GPW) (version 4.11), which covers population in
465 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, and 2020 with spatial resolution of 30 arc-seconds (approx. 1 km at the
466 equator) (<https://earthdata.nasa.gov/data/projects/gpw>). Future population projection (from 2020 to
467 2100) is based on Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP) 2 (Middle of the Road) estimates in 5-year
468 intervals in 30 arc-seconds⁶². This scenario is under medium fertility, mortality, and migration levels,
469 without accounting for policy-directed migration. We calculated the zonal summation based on the
470 overlay of gridded population data with GADM boundary data to get the population for each
471 subnational administration. The population data are then linearly interpolated to get annual
472 estimates.

473 **Gross Domestic and Regional Product**

474 Historical GDP estimates from 1970 to 2020 are from decadal estimates at spatial resolution 0.5-
475 degree grids⁶³. Projected GDP from 2020 to 2100 is based on decadal estimates at a spatial resolution
476 of 0.25 arc-degrees grids⁶⁴. We calculated the zonal summation based on the overlay of gridded GDP
477 data with GADM boundary data to get the GRP for each subnational administration. The GDP data are
478 then linearly interpolated to get the annual estimates.

479 **Emissions targets**

480 At the national level, the emissions targets under countries' NDCs are based on a 2022 study⁶⁵, and
481 specifically its latest update (March 2023)⁶⁶ of the unconditional pledges. We use the average of the
482 "high" and "low" estimates, including "hot air" to strictly represent pledged levels. These targets are
483 excluding land-use emissions, consistently with the allocations calculated in this work.

484 In this paper, we compare the fair share calculated for local governments with their respective
485 emissions targets for 160 regional governments (such as states, provinces and prefectures) and 68

486 cities, for 2030 from Song et al. (2024)¹⁸. The target data was matched to its corresponding
487 administrative geometry using the ClimActor package^{67,68}. These voluntary targets have
488 heterogeneous transparency and do not all specify the baseline year, the Global Warming Potential
489 used, and which GHGs are included. The inclusion of land use in the scope of the target is also not
490 always specified. The scopes of local emissions targets and the assumptions underlying consumption
491 versus territorial accounting are not always disclosed. Here, we consider the emissions targets to apply
492 equally to all GHG emissions excluding land use, thus we applied the targets reductions rates to the
493 Scope 1 emissions from the baseline year, in line with the allocations calculated. When no reference
494 year is indicated, we apply the emissions reduction to the latest historical emissions data available,
495 2022. A pledged emissions pathway is hypothesized as a linear trajectory between current emissions
496 levels and pledges, which provides an estimate for 2030 levels for jurisdictions with only a net-zero
497 target.

498 **Global emissions scenarios**

499 The emissions allocation formulas can be applied to a broad range of global emissions scenarios over
500 the century, including the scenarios presented in the IPCC-AR6 report and hosted online
501 (<https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ar6>). The results presented in this study focus on selected “Illustrative
502 Mitigation Pathway” to provide an illustrative representation of the 1.5°C and well below 2°C
503 alignment. However, any other global emissions scenarios, possibly based on sufficiency
504 considerations can be used. The IMP-GS is the only IMP with a likelihood of limiting peak warming
505 below 2°C (likelihood over 67%) that does not limit warming to 1.5°C. Amongst the three IMPs that
506 limit warming to 1.5°C (likelihood over 50%) with no or limited overshoot, IMP-Ren does not achieve
507 net-zero emissions as required in the Paris Agreement, and the IMP-SP pursues social goals in addition
508 to the 1.5°C threshold with slightly higher emissions than the IMP-LD in the near term (see Figure 3.6
509 in ref.⁴²). While other scenarios of the C1 and C3 categories can reflect 1.5°C and 2°C alignments
510 respectively, with their own socioeconomic narratives, only their positive and negative global
511 emissions (excluding LULUCF) will influence the allocation results.

512

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